

FROM THE HISTORY OF ARCHITECTURAL MONUMENTS OF THE CITY OF BUKHARA (IN THE CASE OF MOKHI KHOSA)

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Abstract. *In this article, thoughts are expressed about the Moxi Khosa structure, one of the ancient and eternal Bukhara's architectural monuments with a deep history, which has made a great contribution to the development of the spiritual and material civilization of mankind for thousands of years, and the history of its construction is explained.*

Key words: *Bukhara, Mokhi Khossa, Amir Olimkhan, Koryogdi Jumayev, master Shirin Murodov, art of urban planning.*

ИЗ ИСТОРИИ АРХИТЕКТУРНЫХ ПАМЯТНИКОВ ГОРОДА БУХАРЫ (НА ПРИМЕРЕ МОХИ ХОСЫ)

Аннотация. *В данной статье высказываются мысли о строении Мокси Хоса, одном из древних и вечных архитектурных памятников Бухары с глубокой историей, внесшем большой вклад в развитие духовной и материальной цивилизации человечества на протяжении тысячелетий, и излагается история его строительства.*

Ключевые слова: *Бухара, Мокхи Хоса, Амир Олимхан, Корёгди Джумаев, мастер Ширин Муродов, искусство градостроительства.*

INTRODUCTION

There are many holy and prestigious cities in the world. But it is rare to find among them those who have successfully passed the tests of history for centuries and are boldly striving towards the future while maintaining the status of greatness. Bukhara is a city that has become a symbol of ancient history and culture, national identity, knowledge, religion, goodness, prosperity and peace, love and loyalty to the Motherland. It is worth being proud of our city of Bukhara, which has a history of almost three thousand years.

The summer residence of the Bukhara emirs, Sitorayi Mokhi Khosa, is a wonderful complex that combines the exquisite architectural art of the East and folk arts and crafts of the 19th and 20th centuries. In any architectural complex in Central Asia, the patterns of the masters who created it have not been so harmonized with the gloss of the beautiful objects inside the palace.

This is the reason why so many poets sang his praises.

DISCUSSIONS AND RESULTS

There are different narratives about the construction history of Sitorayi Mokhi Khosa Palace. The emir of Bukhara, Muzaffar Khan, has an unrivaled and beloved wife, whose name is Sitorabonu. Unfortunately, Sitorabonu's life was short, she gave birth to Abdulahad Khan with a thousand pains and died herself. After that, the emir, deeply saddened, decided to name the summer palace that his father had started to build in order to perpetuate the name of his beloved wife.

Amir's goal was to build a magnificent palace in honor of his beloved wife called¹ "Sitorayi Mokhi Hossa", that is, the star in the heart and the moon, which is its reflection in the sky, and turn it into a paradise on earth. There are many such and similar stories. In fact, this legend is true and Muzaffar Khan named the palace after his beloved wife Sitorabonu. However, historical evidence confirming this has not yet been found.

It was not easy to choose a place for the palace. The ruler called all the wise men to him and ordered to choose a place for the future palace that would be cool in summer and warm in cold winter. In order to identify such a place, they advised to slaughter and hang one sheep at the four gates of Bukharai Sharif facing the four directions of the world. Since the meat of the sheep hanging at the gate of Samarkand spoiled after all, His Eminence ordered to build the palace four miles outside of this gate. This is just a story, according to historical sources², Nasrullah

Khan founded the palace of Sitarayi Mokhi Khosa. However, no part of the palace built during Nasrullah Khan's time has been preserved.

There are many buildings built by rulers in Bukhara, which surpass each other in beauty.

Examples of these are the settlements built by Mangit rulers in the Sherbudin and Karman fortresses, the Sumitan chorbog built many years ago near the current Chorbakr mausoleum, Bogi Bozorcha around Sitorayi Moxi Khosa, Flower chorbogi, Lbayi-gulkoron, Dilkusho, Chorboghi Khossa, Bogishamol-Faiziabad, Gurbin gardens and a number of structures. Unfortunately, they have not survived to this day. The only example of the summer palaces of the rulers that have reached us in a relatively good condition in Central Asia is Sitorayi Mokhi Khosa, the history of its construction spans more than a century and a half.

According to the traditions that have reached us, Muzaffar Khan carefully approached the small details of the construction of this palace, and even showed enthusiasm in the construction works. However, unfortunately, the structures built in the residence during Muzaffar Khan's time have not been preserved. The neighboring hotel, which has been under renovation for many years, also collapsed in 1986, and only its picture has been preserved.

The old palace of Amir was built during Muzaffar Khan's time, at the end of the 19th century, by master Khoja Hafiz, master Nasrullabai, master Ostanqul and others. It consisted of a compact complex of buildings, and stood out as a central building designed in the style of European architecture among the elaborate residences of the rich Bukhara house type. Its front side is enriched with symmetric, sharp shapes and a peshayvan³. Local officials and rich people were received in the old palace, and tsarist officials in the new palace.

The palace buildings, which were built during the reign of Abdulahad Khan and have reached our times, have a unique structure. The rectangular room in it is the heart of the palace.

On either side of the large room are a pair of smaller octagonal halls, facing each other and uniformly polished. A symbolic staircase made of stone formed a unique platform between these two halls. The two sides of the platform are built in a circular shape, and the columns decorated with decorations on the bottom and top give special freshness to the entrance ways.

¹ Жумаев Қ. Ситораи Моҳи Хосса. –Бухоро: Бухоро, 2010. –Б.41.

² Н. Наимов. Бухорои Шариф.-Бухоро: Бухоро, 2005.-Б.45.

³ Бухоро шарк, дурдонаси.-Тошкент: Шарк,.1997.-Б.172

The ruler's throne is placed on the west side of the platform. Sitting in it, Abdulahad Khan saw not only the upper room, but also the guests sitting in a pair of octagonal halls.

In the buildings built by Muzaffar Khan and Abdulahad Khan, the application of the oriental architectural style of the Bukhara and Isfahan schools is only partially visible⁴. It's not for nothing. Both rulers tried to use the Western style, which was new to Bukhara architecture. A group of craftsmen went to Yalta and Petersburg in order to use the western style in the construction of the palace. In addition, the Russian engineer Sakovich was invited to Bukhara to supervise the construction of the residence.

Unfortunately, by the time of Muzaffar Khan and Abdulahad Khan, the buildings built in the residence have been destroyed, and most of them have been seriously damaged. Because of this, it is difficult to find their history. At the same time, the history of the palace of Sitorayi Mokhi Khosa, drawn on thin silk paper, is kept in the background of the manuscripts of the Bukhara State Museum of Art and Architecture. The inscriptions in it are written in Arabic and written in Persian.

Many sheds, ponds, boxes, pavilions and circular elephant houses in history have not been preserved to us. Unfortunately, the author of the history is unknown. He did not write down his name. The main buildings of the settlement in its current form were built during the reign of Mir Sayyid Alim Khan, the last representative of the Mangit dynasty.

Therefore, the structure of the residence is divided into old and new palaces, and the term "old" refers to buildings built before the reign of Olim Khan. During his time, 300 peasants and soldiers were brought to Sitorayi Mokhi Hossa, they drained the swamp, dug a pond and built a garden for two years. In 1911-1914, Bukhara craftsmen built three buildings in this garden according to the project of engineer Margulis: a reception hall, a private building, and a harem. Masters Abdurahim Hayatov and Shirin Murodov, plasterers Khojaqul, Hajiqurban, woodcarvers Qori Chubin, Abdugofur, and painter Hasanjon took part in this construction.

The porch and the White Hall were built in 1912-1914, and the building next to the pool was built in 1917-1918. Amir Olimkhan highly appreciated the work of the masters who participated in the construction of the palace and gave them gifts.

In the last years of Amir Alim Khan's reign, he lived in his summer palace, almost did not interfere in the management of state affairs, and rarely went to Ark fortress. As a result, the country's defense weakened, and Bukharai Sharif was occupied by the Bolsheviks. Thus, in the 50s of the 20th century, our priceless cultural heritage was ideologized, and irreparable damage was caused to the palace of Sitorayi Mokhi Khosa and its surroundings. Many unique objects are looted, rare trees, plants and animals are destroyed. Independence put an end to all this.

CONCLUSION

In conclusion, in honor of independence, the palace of Sitorayi Mokhi Khosa was renovated. By the decision of Damir Yodgorov, the governor of Bukhara region in 1991, the garden of the palace and part of the buildings of the sanatorium were returned. Bukhara is a city with a centuries-old culture that has maintained its importance to this day.

⁴ Жумаев Қ. Ситораи Моҳи Хосса. –Бухоро: Бухоро, 2010. –Б.48.

Every year, the flow of tourists from different parts of the world is increasing in order to enjoy the beauty of its unique architectural monuments and ensembles, to admire the creativity of the masters of practical art who are carefully preserving the centuries-old traditions of their craft, and simply to enjoy the breath of history. Studying the history of these and similar magnificent buildings, which are among the jewels of history, serves to increase the passionate love for our Motherland in each of us.

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